

Characteristics Of Determination Of The Biosphere's Ecological Balance By Spiritual And Moral Factors

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ABSTRACT

The article analyzes aspects of the biosphere's ecological balance related to spiritual and moral factors and issues of their interconnection. The role of human spirituality and moral values in ensuring the stability of the biosphere, the importance of ecological consciousness and culture are highlighted. The influence of spiritual and moral factors in solving ecological problems, their determining characteristics and mechanisms are investigated. The role and prospects of spiritual and moral development of society in maintaining the balance of the biosphere are also considered.

Keywords: biosphere, ecological balance, spiritual and moral factors, determination, ecological consciousness, ecological culture, spiritual values, nature protection, environmental responsibility, sustainable development, biosphere stability, ecological security.

INTRODUCTION

All relations in society - be it social, economic, political or cultural - are closely related to the relationship between nature, society and man. These relations are based on a number of factors, including the norms of ecological ethics. It is becoming clear that this trend will increase further in the future.

This can be justified by the following aspects:

Firstly, any social relationship, regardless of whether it is realized or not by members of society, occurs in the nature-society-man system and therefore is subject to certain ethical rules.

Secondly, since each part of this system is interconnected, an integrated approach and ethical criteria are required to manage them.

Thirdly, the principles of ecological ethics take precedence over other forms of social consciousness and assume the responsibility of

protecting the future of humanity from environmental threats.

Fourth, since each element in the system has its own development characteristics, it is necessary to apply different ethical standards in their management.

In general, studying the interaction of ecological ethical standards with other forms of social consciousness in managing relations between nature and society allows us to understand the laws of ecological and social development and predict future changes.

The ecological ethical standards that determine the relations between nature and society can be considered in two interpretations, the first of which is that these standards are practically manifested in everyday life - the ecological culture, spiritual level and adherence to ethical principles of each person are manifested in their own way.

On the other hand, the specific natural conditions of each region, the procedure for using natural

resources there, and the attitude towards certain elements of nature lead to the formation of special ecological ethical rules. This, in turn, creates the need to increase the effectiveness of these standards.

The level of effectiveness of environmental ethics depends on its objective and subjective factors, as Kh.Kh. Pulatov describes in his dissertation on the topic “Objective and subjective factors of the formation of a culture of nature protection in rural areas” as follows: “The fact that the historically formed production method in Central Asia has formed a special type of ecological culture shows its individuality and difference from others”[1]. However, his views on the aspects related to the agrarian sphere, the relative conservatism of national and religious traditions, and the unconventional nature of environmental protection are somewhat controversial, which can be explained as follows: First, in modern times, the industrialization of agricultural production and the intensification of urbanization processes in the way of life affect the ecological consciousness of the rural population. This process leads to an increase in the ecological intellectual potential of the rural population, which is manifested as an important subjective factor in eliminating indifference and negligence towards nature.

Secondly, the revival of national and religious ecological values and their creative development contribute to the formation of modern socio-moral relations related to nature protection. Thirdly, the globalization of environmental problems and their aggravation, as well as the development of communication systems for international ecological information exchange, serve to overcome "conservative" and "conformist" moods. Fourthly, the modern education system, despite the existing organizational shortcomings, plays an important role in the formation of spiritual and moral relations between the population towards

nature through pedagogical and didactic activities. For these reasons, an institutional system for organizing "nature-society-human" relations on the basis of moral norms and principles has been formed in our region, and certain successes are being achieved in the regions.

Literature review. The global expansion of environmental threats indicates the need for international cooperation to eliminate their negative consequences. This, in turn, is causing universal ecological values to become increasingly important. This situation should be accepted as a natural process, since it is an objective law of development that reflects the harmony of national and universal ecological values. In the words of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh. Mirziyoyev, “The incredibly rich and diverse culture of the Uzbek people has been formed and flourishing for thousands of years in a series of bright historical events, as a result of the unique nature of our country and the inspiring influence of different cultures on each other”[2].

The complexity of regulating the “nature-society-human” relations on the basis of ethical norms can be justified by the following two aspects. On the one hand, the legal basis of these relations depends on the level of development of society, and on the other hand, the limited possibilities of satisfying human needs for natural resources, which often leads to a departure from established ethical boundaries.

Proper spiritual and moral management of human material needs is one of the main conditions for maintaining ecological balance in the biosphere. However, throughout history, the prioritization of material needs in various states and societies has led to the relegation of ecological and moral values to the second level. As a result, environmental problems have become even more acute.

“Today, the development and prosperity of any state is so closely intertwined not only with its close

and distant neighbors, but also with other regions and territories on a global scale that it is not difficult to understand and comprehend that the exclusion of any country from this process will not lead to positive results”[3]. Therefore, the harmony of political methods, legal acts, and moral norms aimed at managing the “nature-society-human” relations is an important factor in environmentally sustainable development.

Research Methodology. The effectiveness of organizing “nature-society” relations depends on the ecological legal culture of citizens, their understanding of their moral duties and responsibilities, and their political activity. The composition of the spiritual and moral factors of the ecological balance of the biosphere has a complex-systemic character and necessitated the emergence of such directions as “ecological law”, “ecological policy”, “ecological economics”, “ecological technology” and others. The common aspects of these directions are characterized by their study based on the norms and principles of ecological morality. Indeed, if political, legal, economic, and other directions of ecological activity are not “regulated” by spiritual and moral norms, their humanistic content may be undermined. From this perspective, their ecological spiritual and moral determinism has been attracting the attention of researchers in this field. For example, B. Valiev’s monograph “Economic Culture and Factors of Its Formation” highlights the features of the integration of economic culture with ecological spiritual and moral norms. According to the author, “in the current period, the process of pluralism and social diversity in economic culture and its deepening of the process of harmonization is covering all spheres of social life”[4].

Such views are also expressed in a number of works by G.T. Tulemetova. In particular, according to the scientist, “ethical problems of an interdisciplinary approach to the problem are of

great importance in studying the axiological aspects”[5]. From this perspective, the axiobiographic approach of Central Asian ethicists to spiritual and moral problems is of methodological importance. However, this approach, in our opinion, is not without some shortcomings. In particular, the artificial theorization of the problem, its remoteness from concrete reality and practice, the marginalization of ecological culture in the life values of entrepreneurs is noticeable. However, in the current era, the system that determines the character and level of development of any entrepreneurship is prioritizing ecological spiritual and moral values.

If we look at the issue more broadly, as a result of the unification of social relations in various fields and their expansion on a global scale, universal moral norms aimed at maintaining the ecological balance in the biosphere are also taking on a common form. In this process, national ecological values and universal ecological principles are developing in an interconnected manner, becoming complementary and reinforcing factors.

In managing the “nature-society-human” relations: the problem of ensuring the compatibility of political instruments, legal laws, and moral norms depends, first of all, on the organizational aspects of the functional activity of the structural elements of the institutional system that implements management. Therefore, ensuring the harmony of politics, law, and morality in the process of managing the “nature-society” relations has always been of great importance in finding solutions to environmental problems. Because organizing nature protection based on the discipline of obedience to legal laws and moral norms creates the possibility of environmentally sustainable development. Analysis and results. The historical experiences of the short period after Uzbekistan gained independence created real opportunities for restoring and developing national ecological

values, forgotten during the era of the authoritarian regime. In particular, the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Islam Karimov, identified the following as the foundations of spirituality: 1) loyalty to universal human values; 2) restoration and development of the spiritual heritage of our people; 3) the practical manifestation of human freedom; 4) patriotism, have also acquired important theoretical and methodological significance in the development of the spiritual and moral foundations of nature protection[6]. Indeed, the construction of “nature-society-man” relations on the basis of spiritual and moral values is a priority factor ensuring its effectiveness and serves to ensure environmentally sustainable development. The tasks in this regard arise from the existing conditions in the life of each region, country and people. Because, “The ecological problem is relevant in all corners of the Earth. Only the degree of its severity differs in different countries and regions of the world. From this point of view, it can be said with painful clarity that one of the most dangerous zones of ecological disaster has emerged in the Central Asian region”[7].

Today, spirituality is taking an increasingly important place among the factors ensuring the future of human civilization. The fact that spirituality is becoming a key factor influencing other socio-political relations, especially ecological relations, should be accepted as an objective law of modern development.

Especially at the current stage of development of “nature-society-human” relations, ecological spiritual and moral values are gaining importance in the system of factors that determine the prospects for sustainable ecological development.

The current state of “nature-society-human” relations and the aggravation of environmental problems on a global scale require the use of an integrated systematic approach and universal methods in solving these issues.

This process includes a number of important aspects:

Firstly, the mutual harmony and mutual influence of spiritual and moral factors in managing “nature-society-human” relations depends on certain conditions. Secondly, the spiritual and moral principles of managing international ecological relations are implemented freely and voluntarily. Thirdly, the humanistic nature of ecological ethical norms lies in their compliance with the interests of all mankind. Fourthly, the priority of the spiritual and moral factor in managing the “nature-society-man” relations does not exclude other subjective factors. Fifthly, the commonality of local, national, regional and global goals in managing the ecological balance of the biosphere requires the universality of their spiritual and moral foundations.

Based on various scientific sources, it can be said that the issue of the interdependence of spiritual and moral factors governing the “nature-society-man” relations has always occupied an important place in the philosophical views of the East and the West. In the history of philosophy, there have been both supporters and opponents of this issue.

This two-way process can be explained as follows:

1. Although there are different social strata in society, this does not negate the common aspects of their spiritual and moral views on nature.
 2. The main force that can unite different socio-political strata of society around a common goal is law and politics based on spiritual and moral values.
- Conclusions and recommendations. In place of the conclusion, there is a need to put forward the following points: firstly, in the history of mankind, the spiritual and moral norms of managing the “nature-society-human” relations have been determined by the system of social consciousness; secondly, national ecological moral norms are a form of manifestation of universal values in specific

conditions; thirdly, the absolutization of the role of a particular form of social consciousness in managing the “nature-society-human” relations loses its significance if separated from spiritual and moral values; fourthly, the effectiveness of ecological spiritual and moral values in managing the “nature-society-human” relations is an important criterion determining the level of development of society; fifthly, the transformation into life of the integrative activity of forms of social consciousness in managing the “nature-society-human” relations is in the interests of universal humanity; Sixth, in the current period, the need for harmonization of national and universal ecological moral norms and its theoretical and methodological foundations is increasing.

Based on the increasing role and importance of spiritual and moral factors in maintaining the ecological balance of the biosphere, the following aspects should be highlighted:

1. In the current conditions of globalization, solving ecological problems can be achieved not only through technical or economic solutions, but also by relying on spiritual and moral values.
 2. In the “nature-society-man” relationship, spiritual and moral factors serve as the main source of strength determining all other socio-political relationships.
 3. Harmonization of national and universal ecological values is one of the important conditions for solving modern ecological problems.
 4. The role of ecological culture and moral norms in the life of society is increasingly strengthened, and this process is becoming an objective law of the development of civilization.
 5. In maintaining the ecological balance of the biosphere, the common interests of different social strata, states and peoples are being united on the basis of spiritual and moral values.
- In general, the increasing importance of spiritual and moral factors in maintaining the ecological

balance of the biosphere and solving environmental problems has become one of the important features of modern development. This, in turn, requires a responsible approach to the future of humanity and raising environmental awareness.

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